

Accounting Treatment of Research and development

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October,2022

Introduction

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Organizations seeking to break even and remain afloat must effect research-based changes in areas ailing them. These changes can include top-down operational infrastructure changes with talent identification getting extended to the makeshift staff constituted from all parts and levels of the company to help mitigate the problems temporarily during these happenings. The changes though would follow the existing procedures of process mapping, cause analysis and cross-discipline cooperation and further improvement of processes and

technology. For such changes to be effected, extensive research must be done and invested upon with long term positive outcomes for the improvement of service delivery. Despite the established importance of research and development in streamlining operations as well as growth, many companies still struggle to account costs invested in research and development. This paper looks into the international guidelines to the accounting treatment of research and development costs.

Delimitation of definitions according to HGB and IAS

Research is planned original investigation or study done gain new scientific and technological insight, knowledge and understanding. A company undertakes a research to develop new strategies. Development, on the other hand, is defined as the application of the research findings or other knowledge in planning and designing of the production process for substantially improved materials, devices, products, processes, services and systems before commercial use or production.

Recognition of development costs

Accounting Methodology

IISAB38 demands that expenditure on research be deemed as not having future economic benefits and therefore its capitalization does comply with the accruals concept. This means that the treatment of this kind of expenditure is to write it off to the incurred profit and loss account. Consequently, expenditure on the costs of development, as a basic rule, should be written off to the profit and loss account as incurred as with the research expenditures. Under ISAB38, there is an option to defer expenditure and carry it forward as an intangible asset if it meets the following criteria.

The project is clearly defined, commercially viable and technically feasible, the expenditure is separately identifiable, there are available resources to complete the project and the income of the project outweighs the project cost. If the requirements are fully met, the company may choose to capitalize the costs and bring them on balance sheet and maintain the policy to write costs off to the profit and loss account. It should be noted that if the company decides to adopt an accounting policy of capitalization, the same application should be consistent and replicated in the treatment of all development projects that meet the criteria.

Accounting of development costs according to HGB and IFRS

Approach criteria

Investment in research and development can be referred to as an intangible business asset that has no physical form. Tangible assets, on the other hand, can be seen or touched with clear outcome predictability. In business, there are two types of intangible assets, namely, those that are internally generated and those that are purchased. Accounting treatment of the purchased ones are straight forward with its purchase capital purchased in the same way as tangible assets. Internally generated assets require a careful consideration. Research and development costs in business are categorized as internally generated intangible assets and therefore must be carefully looked at before accounting with recognition to the host country and international regulations and standards¹ (Statista, 2020).

¹ Statista (Jun 9, 2020) Aerospace and defense companies with the highest spending on research and development (R&D) in 2019. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1102967/global-research-and-development-top-aerospace-defense-spenders/>

In the United States, treatment of research and development in accounting are different from many places worldwide. Under the United States accounting standards, intangible assets are accounted using FRS rules of Goodwill and intangibles. The treatment of research and development is governed by its own accounting standards despite the fact than they are intangible assets in the United States.

Evaluation criteria

From an economic perspective, it will be reasonable to capitalize research and development costs regardless of the fact that its benefits cannot be estimated. For asset value to be estimated for capitalization, the number of years needed for the investment to generate benefit has t be estimated and will be subject to amortization period assumption. Amortization life differs from one asset to another and reflects the economic life of investments. For amortization life of an research and development investment must be estimated, information is gathered on the past years expenses on the investment. The expenses incurred during the amortization life are obtained as a way of evaluation.

The cost of intangible assets separately acquired, according to IAS 38 comprise of its purchase price together with import duties and non-refundable taxes less rebates and discounts and any directly attributable costs or asset preparation for intended use. The subsequent measurement of intangible is a very similar property as equipment, plant and property. For the subsequent evaluation, two models, cost model and revaluation models can be used² (Moxter, 1981). The cost model demands the evaluation of intangible costs is carried out by its cost less accumulated amortization, just like depreciations are handled, less any accumulated impairment

² Moxter, A., (1981) *Immaterielle Anlagewerte im neuen Bilanzrecht*, pp 821-825

loss. In the revaluation model, intangible assets are carried at a fair value at revaluation date less accumulated amortization less any accumulated impairment loss.

The revaluation model is not frequently applied for intangible assets since it demands the existence of an active market, which is rare.

Designation criteria

Under IFRS rules, expense on research is treated as an expense, as it is done under GAAP. By contrasting IFRS and GAAP, development costs can be capitalized if the company established that the development is commercially viable. The IFRS approach is that some research and development cost can be capitalized instead of being incurred as an expense in the profit and loss statement. IFRS requires subjectivity and judgment which creates risk management give room for optimism. Research and development is a long term investment in the company as the results will be seen in successive years to come in revenue increase, cash flow and profit and thus, should be capitalized, rather than being listed as an expense. Without the capitalization of research and development spending, it will be difficult to compare with companies in the industry. This is because spending on research and development may have a big impact on other companies' bottom lines in the year.

Practical example for the accounting of development costs at Goodrich Lighting Systems GmbH, a part of Collins Aerospace

The company consider system that are in place with a view upgrading the data level captured many years before transition to international Accounting standards. The impact of transitioning to international accounting standards may affected the existing technology. The research concept is similar to accounting bases such as capitalization of development costs and far reaching effects of the organization (Britzelmaier, 2017). The company works under US generally accepted Accounting principles (GAAP), which has many accounting pronouncements that govern

accounting research and development costs. In the effect of the requirements to capitalize research and development costs, the company follows the United States standards, However, with the need to transition t international standards, mid and long term research and development contracts are affected³ (Buchholz, 2015).

Capitalization of research and development is more conservative than expensing. When it is capitalized, it is not put on the balance sheet and impacts the income statement and vanishes. Once Research and development is capitalized, it's amortized over the useful life. Capitalization of research and development grows the balance sheet by the value of the investment; it reduces return on investment and impacts asset return.

Research and development depreciation expense impacts the income statement as the value is amortized over the life. Doing this smoothes the artificial volatility of return and development expense and is reflects the investment for the management needs for its daily operations.

Example

The total of 100, 000 was spent on research and development in the company. The residua; value was 20,000 as the product commercial life developed over a five year period. The amortization expense used a straight-line method.

Total Research spending 100,000

Residual value 20,000

³ Buchholz, R., (2015) *Internationale Rechnungslegung. Ansatz von Research and Development Costs* pp.67-71.

Commercial life 5 years

Amortization 20%

Year	Asset value (Start year)	amortization	Asset value (End year0)
1	100,000	16000	84,000
2	84,000	16,000	68,000
3	68,000	16,000	52,000
4	52,000	16,000	36,000
5	36,000	16,000	20,000

Based on the above results, the company had 16,000 amortization expenses annually for the five years until it accrues to the residual value of 20,000. Through amortization, the five year cost, the net income of the company is smooth and expenses closely match revenues.

Retrospective measurement of activated development costs

The treatment of capitalized developments costs in The US requires that where development costs are considered as assets, the costs should be amortized over periods expected to earn the benefit. The amortization of the costs should be done only once commercial production has started or when the product or service sold starts being used. Each capitalized project is reviewed at the end of every accounting period so that recognition criteria are met. The

capitalized costs should be written off to profit and loss account where the stated criteria are not met⁴ (Steuer-Fachschule, 2019).

The newer international accounting standards have more different demands when it comes to treating research and development costs as compared to how they are handled in the United States. The United States allows the choice over capitalization and can result in inconsistencies between different companies. Some of the criteria are subjective and choice can be manipulated by companies that want to capitalize on development costs (Born, 2001).

International treatment of research and development takes a slightly separate standard. The international standards are dealt with under IAS 38 Intangible assets. The IAS recognizes intangible assets as one that has prospective economic benefits from assets and will flow to the company and that whose cost is reliably measured. This criterion is straightforward but can be difficult to assess whether or not they have been met. The recognition of internally generated intangible assets is clearer with IAS 38 as it separates research and development projects into research and development phases (Steuer-Fachschule, 2019).

In the research phase, it is impossible to demonstrate the future economic benefit of the investment. The IAS 38 states that the expenditure incurred here are written off to the income statement as an expense and should not be capitalized as an intangible asset (Dinh, Kopf and Schultze, 2017).

Conclusion

⁴ Steuer-Fachschule (2019). Heinz Boderius. Jahresabschluss Analyse Teil A: Bilanzierung – und Bewertungsgrundsätze nach Handelsrecht.

Many businesses worldwide spend vast amounts of money annually to research and development of products and services. This is done by companies in pursuit for increased income in the years to come. In the coming future, economic benefit is expected to flow to the company that invests in research and development. These costs, generally, would be treated as assets rather than expenses as they meet the definition of an asset as described by IASB and Statement of Principles. Some arguments posit that it is impossible to predict the outcome of this form of investment project in the future. In reaction to this, the international accounting standards give accountants more information on how to clarify the situation.

For organizations to stay competitive, they must invest in research and development projects to make it more productive and knowledgeable. Development opportunity provision helps attract high-quality employees and helps retain those that can assist to contribute to business growth. The use of consultants helps align training and development of accountants with organizational goals and international standards. They help oversee accounting personnel training programs and budgets, organize training programs, create or select course content and materials.

Organization must invest in modern accounting practices to compete internationally. Research, development, consulting, advising and designing of accounting systems as well as coach, guide and train staff come in handy in meeting international standards of accounting as well as enhancing competition. The development of management and supervisory skills, defining organizational missions, goal and objectives as well as assess situations and improve the performance of work must be achieved through research and development through the use of consultants. Additionally, they can identify training and operational needs, improve communication within an organization, boost employee motivation and enlarge customer base

An effective training program follows systematic steps to meet organizational objectives and participant expectations.

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